

Determinants of Severity of Abdominal Wall Hernias and Outcomes of Surgical Repair in Rural Southeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In developing nations, abdominal wall hernias constitute a very common cause of considerable morbidity and mortality especially in rural communities. In many communities across Africa, the shift towards elective repair is far from desired and many cases still present late with complications. This study aimed to determine the severity, morbidity and mortality of abdominal wall hernias and outcomes of surgical repair in rural Southeast Nigeria. It was a cross-sectional study of adult patients surgically treated for abdominal wall hernia in rural southeast Nigeria between June 2015 to May 2018. A total of 794 patients were recruited; 629 (79.2%) had uncomplicated hernias while 165 (20.8%) presented acutely. Inguinal hernias comprised 76.1% of the hernias, followed by umbilical hernia (8.1%). Patients with Inguino-scrotal / inguino-labial hernia represent 64.2% of all cases. Over a quarter (189, 23.8%) had comorbidities, 13.6% harbored recurrent hernias while 53.7% had hernias with defect sizes 5cm or more. Morbidity rates were 40.0% in emergency repairs, 40.4% in the elderly and 31.2% in those with comorbidities. The major determinants of morbidity were emergency presentation ($p=0.000$), advancing age ($p=0.000$), procedures performed by lower rank of surgeon ($p=0.000$), extent of hernia ($p=0.029$) and voluminous sizes ($p=0.000$). Overall, mortality rate was 2.0%, but 8.5% in those with emergency presentation. The independent predictors of mortality were intestinal resection ($p=0.000$) and comorbidities ($p=0.002$). A surgeon in the rural setting encounters high proportion of complex hernias and patients often present in emergency with coexisting medical diseases leading to high morbidity and mortality rates

Keywords: Abdominal hernia, Prognostic, Mortality, Recurrence, Mesh

INTRODUCTION

In developing nations, abdominal wall hernias constitute a very common cause of considerable morbidity and mortality, especially in rural communities

where basic health facilities and competent health providers are scarcely available.^{1,2,3} Hitherto, giant inguinal hernias having the size of human head or even bigger were

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described in Africans.^{4,5} Some extended below the knee and led to accommodation of several viscera in a typical manner described as “loss of domain.”^{4,6} Fortunately, this trend appears to be changing in the African sub-region and other developing countries due to upsurge in health facilities and a rise in number of medically qualified personnel who can undertake hernia repair.^{1,4} Nevertheless, in many rural communities across Africa and other resource-constrained nations, the shift towards elective repair is far from desired, and many cases still present late with a plethora of complications and mortality that markedly outstrip the western rates.^{1,3,4,7,8,9,10}

Recent published data on elective inguinal hernia repair from our environment showed that up to 37.3% of the patients harbored complete inguinoscrotal hernias, 17.2% had bilateral hernias while 17.5% of the patients presented in emergency.⁸ It was also observed that 50.2% (131) of the patients waited between six to 20 years before presentation.⁸ The burden is the same across other African nations and India.^{1,9,10} In Northern Ghana, 90.7% of all patients with abdominal wall hernia were young and aged 21-40 years and for inguinal hernias, 84.7% were indirect.¹¹ Worst still, a fifth (20.1%) of the 1,330 patients harbored recurrent hernias and 83.1% of these recurrences were in the young, aged 21-40 years.¹¹ From the foregoing, the burden of the unmet needs for hernias in many parts of low and middle-income countries (LMICs) is unprecedented and requires accelerated, system wide approaches.

Published data on abdominal wall hernias in Africa are poorly documented and investigators working in the continent are still in oblivion regarding the extent of severity of the disease in the region.³ It has been cited that across many regions in the developing nations, a significant proportion of hernias are operated on emergency setting due to lack of income to cover the cost of elective surgery and inaccessibility to appropriately equipped hospitals.^{1,3,11} These hernias, commonly longstanding and voluminous, occurring in patients with multiple comorbidities, often time patients being unaware of their comorbid conditions, are therefore left

untreated resulting in high morbidity and mortality rates.^{3,7,9}

This deplorable situation is particularly severe in the rural settlements where medical facilities and personnel are in acute shortage and poverty, ignorance and socio-cultural barriers significantly limit access to safe surgical services.^{1,3,7,9} The magnitude of the burden of a common, but neglected surgical disease like hernia may not be fully appreciated in our context until the state-of-the art among rural dwellers is reported. There is no organized previous documentation on this aspect of the subject in our environment, despite the large volume of hernia cases in our rural practice. This study aimed to document the determinants of severity and treatment outcomes of abdominal wall hernias in rural Southeast Nigeria.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Design and Setting

This is a cross-sectional study of all consecutive patients with abdominal wall hernia repaired surgically from June 2015 to May 2018. This was a multi-centre study carried out at Bishop Shanahan Specialist Hospital, Nsukka, Enugu State and Mater Misericordiae Specialist Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State both in Southeast Nigeria.

Study Population

Initially, all patients aged 16 years and above who presented with abdominal wall hernia were seen and counselled for operative repair. Only those who gave consent were included in this study. Seven hundred and ninety-four (794) out of 820 patients with abdominal wall hernia met the inclusion criteria and were further evaluated and scheduled for either emergency or elective hernia repair. Moribund patients and those with metastatic intra-abdominal malignancy were excluded. Informed consent was obtained from all the patients before they were recruited into the study.

Ethical Approval

The protocol for this study was approved by the research and ethics committee of both hospitals before

commencement of the study. The study was conducted in accordance with the 'Declaration of Helsinki'. All ethical principles relating to studies on human subjects were observed during the study period.

Procedure

At the initial contact, each patient was assessed clinically; socio-demographic and clinical details were recorded and entered into a proforma. Patients scheduled for emergency operation were admitted through accident and emergency department for assessment and thorough resuscitation before operative repair. Those billed for elective surgery were admitted a day before surgery through surgical outpatient clinic in order to review their laboratory results and avoid unnecessary delay in the morning of surgery since many came from remote rural settlements. Basic investigations like full blood count, serum creatinine, electrolytes and urea and urinalysis were routinely done. Other special tests were done when indicated.

Pre-operatively, patients were assessed for comorbidities and decision taken on the anesthetic procedure suitable for each case. Majority of the anesthetic procedures were done by nurse anesthetics, the rest, mainly obstructed cases were conducted by two visiting specialist anesthesiologists, one for each hospital. After evaluation, findings were discussed with patients and their relatives. In the elective arm, those with voluminous groin hernias, bilateral groin hernias, incisional hernias, large or multiple midline ventral hernias or recurrent hernias were counseled for mesh repair. Those who could not afford cost of mesh implants eventually had their hernias sorted out using suture-based anatomic methods. Before surgery, all active infections were treated, malnutrition and anemia corrected and those at moderate to high risk of deep venous thrombosis (DVT) were commenced on prophylaxis.

Following appropriate skin incision, combined instrument and diathermy dissection was carried out till the sac with its contents was exposed. The type of repair and extent of operation were dependent on whether the

surgery was for elective or emergency repair and whether mesh or anatomic methods were used. Defect size was routinely estimated intra-operatively with finger estimation. Tube drain was inserted when indicated and skin sutures removed on the 10th to 12th post-operative day. Patients were followed up actively for 24 months. They were given first appointment two weeks after discharge, then monthly for three times, followed by three-monthly appointments for three times. Thereafter, six-monthly appointments were scheduled till 24 months. Post-operative complications were noted and recorded. Due to poor road networks and long distance from remote settlements, telephone interviews were arranged for those who default from follow up appointments and a new date re-scheduled.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 23.0 (IBM, Chicago, IL USA, 2015). Data were presented as mean, standard deviations, percentages and tables. The association between different variables was measured and compared using Chi-square (*test*). Confidence interval was calculated at 95% level and significance at 5% probability level ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

Sociodemographic characteristics

During the period under review, 3,974 general surgical patients were seen, but 820, (20.6%) of them had abdominal wall hernias of various types. However, only 794 patients with hernia fulfilled the criteria for inclusion in this study. The 794 patients formed our study cohorts. Of the 794 patients, there were 596 (75.1%) males and 198 (24.9%) females giving a male to female ratio of 3:1. Seventy-three patients harbored bilateral inguinal hernias, accounting for 9.2% of abdominal hernias and 12.1% of the inguinal hernias studied. Overall, there were 867 hernias. Over four-fifth (658, 82.9%) were farmers; the rest were artisans (50, 6.3%), traders (36, 4.5%), civil servants

(22, 2.8%), professionals (10, 1.3%) and others (18, 2.3%). The ages of the patients ranged between 16-84 years with a mean of 42.63 +/- SD 17.10. The peak age incidence was 26-35 years, though about a quarter (194, 24.4%) were aged 56 years and above. Majority (355, 58.8%) of the patients with inguinal hernia were young, aged between 16-44 years.

Clinical presentation

The spectrum of the hernias with respect to the total number of patients diagnosed with the disease included inguinal (604, 76.1%), umbilical (64, 8.1%), paraumbilical (44, 5.5%), epigastric (32, 4.0%), incisional (32, 4.0%), femoral (11, 1.4), spigelian (4, 0.5%) and lumbar (3, 0.4%). This gives a ratio of 3:1 for inguinal versus other abdominal wall hernias, but in the elderly, the ratio is 6:1. Inguinoscrotal/inguinolabial hernia (funicular and complete) represents 64.2% of all inguinal hernias, but 48.9% of the total abdominal wall hernias repaired. Majority (680, 85.6%) of the patients presented after one year from the time of onset of hernia. However, 34 (4.3%) patients presented within six months of noticing their hernias; majority (nine, 26.5%) of the patients in this group harbored incisional hernias (IH). Over half (464, 58.4%) of the patients have lived with their hernias for more than five years before presenting to the specialist surgery clinic. More so, nearly a tenth (72, 9.1%) have harbored hernias beyond 20 years before presentation. Nearly four-fifth (629, 79.2%) presented electively, the rest (165, 20.8%) were admitted as emergencies. The mode of presentation for the various hernia types is shown below (Table 1).

Anesthetic Assessment and Surgical Treatment

The American Association of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) scores of the patients were ASA I (487, 61.3%), ASA II (158, 19.9%), ASA III (137, 17.3%), ASA IV (11, 1.4%) and ASA V (1, 0.1%). A high ASA score was found to be an independent predictor of mortality ($p=0.000$). Majority (469, 59.1%) of the repairs were done under general anesthesia followed by local anesthesia (283,

36.6%). About 48.3% (304 patients) of elective cases were fixed under general anesthesia while 283 (45.0%) patients with uncomplicated hernias had their hernias fixed under local infiltrative anesthesia. The impact of the hernia type and repair techniques on the choice of anesthesia is shown below (Table 2). Emergency presentation is an independent predictor of general and spinal anaesthetic technique ($p=0.026$), but there was no statistically significant difference ($p=0.086$) in the choice of anaesthesia for the various types of hernia, irrespective of emergency or elective status of the patients. Of the 165 patients with emergency presentation, nearly one-tenth (16, 9.7%) had spontaneous reduction and were operated on the next elective operating date. Of the 149 (18.8%) that ultimately had emergency operation, nearly a third (48, 32.2%) had bowel resection with or without stoma; the resection rate for the entire repair in the 794 patients was 6.0%. Of the 102 patients with obstructed or strangulated inguinal hernias, 81 (79.4%) cases were fixed through the inguinal route, the rest (21, 20.6%) were managed through a midline laparotomy incision. The five cases of obstructed/strangulated femoral hernias were repaired through a midline laparotomy. Prosthetic mesh placement was an important independent predictor of general and spinal anaesthetic method for inguinal ($p=0.010$), midline (0.014) and other ($p=0.012$) hernias.

Outcomes of Surgical Treatment

One hundred and thirty-three (16.8%) patients developed post-operative complications, but some had more than one complication, leading to a total of 179 post-operative complications. The commonest complication recorded in this series was wound infection (59, 7.4%), followed by wound hematoma (32, 4.0%). Others include seroma, recurrence, intra-abdominal abscess, anastomotic leakage, visceral injury and chronic pain. The risks of post-operative complications were more on patients with advancing age, recurrent hernias, large hernias, emergency repair and in those with comorbidities (Table 3). Comorbidities were found in 189 patients; hypertension (63, 7.9%), diabetes mellitus (32, 4.05%), bladder outlet

obstruction (30, 3.8%), obesity (24, 3.0%), osteoarthritis (13, 1.6%), chronic respiratory obstruction (10, 1.3%), renal disease (5, 0.6%), chronic liver disease (4, 0.5%), HIV/AIDS (4, 0.5%), tuberculosis (2, 0.3%) and goitre (2, 0.3%). Also, technical and perioperative determinants like rank of surgeon, size of defect and extent of surgery impacted on morbidity rates as shown below (Table 4). The mortality rate was 2.0% (16 deaths). The vast majority (14, 87.5%) of the deaths occurred in cases repaired emergently. The major independent predictors of mortality were emergency presentation (p=0.000), delayed presentation after onset of complications (p=0.008) and intestinal resection (p=0.000) as shown below (Table 5).

Table 1: Mode of presentation

Presentation	Inguinal	Midline	Incisional	Femoral	Others	Total(%)
Simple	468	125	28	4	5	629(79.2)
Irreducible/painful	35	7	2	2	1	47(5.9)
Obstructed	44	5	1	2	1	53(6.7)
Strangulated (+/- gangrene)	58	3	1	3	0	65(8.2)
Total	604	140	32	11	7	794(100.0)

+/- =plus or minus

Table 2: The influence of hernia types and repair techniques on choice of anesthesia.

Parameter	General	Spinal	Local	Total	P-value
Hernia types					
Inguinal	345	38	221	604	0.086
Midline	87	0	53	140	
Incisional	29	2	1	32	
Femoral	4	2	5	11	
Others	4	0	3	7	
Total	469 (59.1)	42 (5.3)	283 (36.6)	794 (100.0)	
Repair techniques:					
Inguinal:					
Nylon darn	120	10	166	296	0.010
Mod. Bassini	104	6	53	163	
Lichtenstein	121	22	2	145	
Midline:					
Simple repair	53	2	50	105	0.014
Onlay mesh	63	0	4	67	
Others:					
Simple repair	4	0	7	11	0.012
Onlay mesh	4	2	1	7	
Total	469 (59.1)	42 (5.3)	283 (36.6)	794 (100.0)	

Mod=modified.

Table 3: Impact of disease and patient-related factors on morbidity rates

Parameter	Frequency	Patients with morbidities	Morbidity Rates (%)	P-value	R.R(95% C.I of R.R)
Age:					
16-44	469	57	12.2	0.000	-
45-64	236	40	16.9		
65-86	89	36	40.4		
Sex:					
Male	596	109	18.3	0.057	1.51(0.99-2.28)
Female	198	24	12.1		
Nature of Hernia:					
Primary	686	107	15.6	0.040	0.65(0.44-0.95)
Recurrent	108	26	24.1		
Comorbidities:					
Present	189	59	31.2	0.000	2.55(1.89-3.45)
Absent	605	74	12.2		
Hernia type:					
Inguinal	604	108	17.9	0.192	-
Midline	172	22	12.8		
Others	18	3	16.7		
Mode of Presentation:					
Elective	629	67	10.7	0.000	0.27(0.20-0.36)
Emergency	165	66	40.0		

†No= number; ‡R.R = Relative Risk

Table 4: Effects of Technical and peri-operative factors on morbidities

Parameters	Frequency	Patients with morbidities	Morbidity Rate (%)	P-value	R.R (95% C.I of R.R)
Rank:					
Med. Officer	296	70	23.6	0.000	2.07(1.50-2.84)
Surgeon	498	57	11.4		
Defect size:					
0-4cm	368	45	12.2	0.000	-
5-10cm	389	74	19.0		
>10cm	37	14	37.8		
Extent of Hernia:					
Bubunocoele	216	21	9.7		
Funicular	153	26	17.1	0.027	-
Complete	236	58	24.6		
Non-inguinal	190	28	14.7		
Extent of surgery:					
Resection	48	27	56.3		
No resection	745	106	14.2	0.000	3.96(2.91-5.37)

†No= number; ‡R= Relative Risk; Med= Medical

Table 5: Clinical and epidemiological determinants of mortality

Parameters	Frequency	No. of Morbidities	Mortality Rate (%)
Mode of presentation			
Elective	629	2	0.3
Emergency	165	14	8.5
P-Value			0.000
RR(95%C.I of RR)			0.038 (0.010-0.163)
Age			
16-44	469	2	0.4
45-64	235	8	3.4
65-86	90	6	6.7
P-value			0.000
Comorbidities			
Present	109	7	6.4
Absent	685	9	1.3
P-value			0.002
RR(95%CI of RR)			4.89 (1.86-12.85)
Delayed presentation (Emergencies only):			
0-12Hours			
13-24Hours	8	0	0.0
25-48Hours	46	2	3.4
>48Hours	66	5	7.6
P-value	45	9	20.0
			0.000
Intestinal Resection:			
Performed	48	11	22.9
Not performed	736	5	0.7
P-value			0.000
RR(95%CI of RR)			33.73 (12.21-93.18)

†No= number; ‡RR=relative risk

DISCUSSION

During the period under review, external abdominal wall hernias accounted for 20.6% of all general surgical procedures performed in the selected hospitals. This value is higher than a figure of 12.5% reported in Zaria,

Nigeria, but comparable to 22.0% quoted in a rural population in India.^{2,10} From the above, it appears abdominal wall hernias are commoner among patients attending rural and semi-urban hospitals. The proportion of

abdominal wall hernia surgery output from the referral hospital in Zaria,² Nigeria was lower, perhaps due to the fact that many other non-hernia specialist general surgical cases were selectively referred to the surgeons and treated in that tertiary hospital. In addition, majority of the hernias that present to the teaching hospitals are referred cases that are selected, while majority of other cases (small, uncomplicated, non-recurrent, ASA I or II) are commonly repaired outside teaching hospitals. Moreover, data from published studies indicate that abdominal wall hernias are commoner among farmers and artisans who traditionally, are predominantly rural and semi-urban dwellers.^{3,8,9}

The age and site-specific distribution of the patients with abdominal wall hernia in this study were similar to observations from Zaria and Ibadan, both in Nigeria.^{2,12} Precisely, inguinal hernias were approximately three times as common as other hernias combined, and in the elderly, this disparity was more prominent. Elsewhere, it has been observed that the incidence of inguinal hernias is higher in the elderly due to progressive weakness of collagen tissue of the abdominal wall and increased basal intra-abdominal pressure with age.^{13,14}

The clues from the relative contributions of multiple predictors evaluated in this study have demonstrated enormous unmet need for hernia and gave credence to earlier reports that there is inadequate clinical and epidemiological data to inform surgeons working in Africa on the severity and outcome of hernia repair in the continent.³ In this report, advanced age at presentation, presence of comorbidities, emergency presentation, large hernia sizes and intestinal resection constitute the most significant predictors of poor postoperative outcomes. It was observed that a higher proportion of elderly patients developed more complications after operative repair compared to patients in other age groups ($p=0.000$). This may be related to higher incidence of comorbidities in these patients as well as lower physiologic reserve and greater tendency to present in emergency with life threatening complications as cited previously by other workers.^{2,4,13,14} Elderly patients had an increased incidence

of necrotic bowel resection when compared with adult series for the same duration of irreducibility.^{13,15} This could be explained by increased vulnerability of entrapped bowel to incarceration and ischemia in those with advanced age. Our findings agree with results from Turkey¹⁵ where comorbidities were present in 45.5% of 189 elderly patients with emergency hernia repair. The authors found that the high morbidity and mortality rates were predicated on the bowel resection, with mortality rate of 19.4% quoted in those that received intestinal resection.¹⁵

Though, only 37(4.7%) of the 794 patients harbored hernias with defects greater than or equal to 10.0cm in diameter, 37.8% of these patients developed post-operative complications compared with 12.2% among patients with hernia defects less than or equal to 3cm in diameter ($p=0.000$). Previous investigators have observed that extensive tissue dissection, distorted anatomy of anterior abdominal wall, loss of domain by abdominal viscera and development contribute to elevated rates of complications and poor outcome after operative repair of longstanding, voluminous hernias.^{3,4,6} In Enugu, Nigeria, 41 consecutive patients with uncomplicated abdominal hernias, selected on the basis of large sizes of their hernias (using defect size greater than 4.0cm in widest diameter as the most important inclusion criterion) were evaluated.⁶ Adverse post-operative outcomes ranged from wound infection in 31.6%, partial wound dehiscence in 21.1%, post-operative respiratory distress in 7.8% to mesh infection and subsequent recurrence in 2.6%.⁶ Perioperative mortality of 4.9% was quoted, with respiratory distress and respiratory failure thought to be responsible for the deaths.⁶ It has been cited that the high rate of failed repairs and post-repair complications and mortality in large, complex hernias may also be related to the high incidence of associated comorbid conditions. The comorbidities not only contribute to the development of the hernia (increased intra-abdominal pressure for instance), but also make the surgery a high-risk procedure.⁶ It has been shown that comorbidities are associated with higher American Society of Anesthesiologist (ASA) score, which in turn is an independent predictor of unfavorable outcome measures.⁹

In this survey, approximately one-fifth (20.8%) of the patients presented in emergency, with complications ranging from incarceration through bowel obstruction to strangulation with or without gangrene (and/or perforation). Overall, nearly half (58, 49.2%) of patients in the obstruction and strangulation groups had intestinal resection with or without stomas. In concert, the duo of emergency presentation and intestinal resection significantly increased morbidity and mortality rates in this study, with 40.0% of all emergency cases developing post-operative complications, rising to 56.3% in those that had bowel resections ($p=0.000$ for emergency repair and $p=0.000$ for intestinal resection) as shown in the results section (Tables 3 and 4). The crux of the matter with emergency presentation and intestinal resection is not only on the number of complications recorded post-operatively, but on the type and severity of these post-operative aftermaths.^{4,9,16} Indeed, all cases of anastomotic leakage and intra-abdominal abscesses, 78% of wound infections and 71.4% of recurrences recorded in this series occurred in individuals who presented with hernia complications and had emergency operation with or without bowel resection. In a related publication, Ohene-Yeboah working in Kumasi, Ghana reported that 65% of hernias repaired in their center were performed for strangulation with an overall bowel resection rate of 24.1% among 120 unselected patients with complicated external abdominal wall hernias.¹⁶ The resection rate was highest among patients with strangulated femoral hernia (50.0%), probably related to danger of missed diagnosis and thus, delay in operation. Previous workers have noted that femoral hernias in elderly women can be mistaken for inflamed lymph nodes or lipomata with serious clinical consequences.^{17,18}

Other independent predictors of poor outcomes following operative repair of abdominal wall hernias were rank of surgeon ($p=0.000$), recurrent state of hernia ($p=0.040$) and extent of inguinal hernia ($p=0.029$). On the other hand, sex and hernia type were not independent predictors of poor outcome in our setting (Table 3). Mba, in Sokoto, Nigeria has expressed concern when he

observed that majority of wound complications in his series occurred in simple elective herniorrhaphy performed by junior rank of surgeons in his center.⁴ The author recommended adequate supervision of surgical trainees as non-observance of requisite strict aseptic technique and meticulous hemostasis were implicated.⁴ The higher adverse outcomes noted in this series may be related to the peculiarities of hernia disease in rural Africa as previously noted by other studies.^{3,4,8,9,12} The major independent predictors of mortality in this study were intestinal resection ($p=0.000$), age 65 years and above ($p=0.000$), delay beyond 24 hours after onset of complication ($p=0.008$) and comorbidities (cardiopulmonary and renal). Previous data from similar studies overlap with the above reports.^{4,6,9,15,17}

We determined that general anesthesia was more popular than other forms of anesthesia for unclear reasons. Though 165 patients who presented in emergency required general or spinal anesthesia, it was surprising that about 48.3% (304 patients) of elective cases were fixed under general anesthesia. This is higher than 45.0% (283 patients) utilization rate for local anesthetic infiltration among patients with uncomplicated hernias. Many authors have observed the predilection of African surgeons and anesthetists for the use of general anesthesia to repair hernias.^{3,5,7,8,9} Perhaps, the high incidence of huge hernias, recurrent cases and bilateral inguinal hernias informed the decision for higher utilization of general anesthesia in hernias repaired electively in this series. Generally, prosthetic mesh implants necessitated more frequent use of general anesthesia, probably due to a need for better muscle relaxation, more tissue dissection and occurrence of voluminous hernias that required mesh implantation. In Ibadan, Nigeria, however, 67.8% of the hernias repaired were sorted out as day cases using local infiltrative anesthesia.¹² The authors ascribed the success of ambulatory hernia surgery in their unit to excellent surgical training programs enshrined in long practice of surgical management of all forms of hernias in their institution.¹²

CONCLUSION

Findings from this study indicates that abdominal wall hernias constitute a high workload for the general surgeons working in rural hospitals compared to their counterparts in urban referral centres. A surgeon in rural setting encounters more complex abdominal wall hernias coexisting with multiple medical illnesses, and often times, the patients present late either in emergency or electively with attendant high morbidity and mortality.

Recommendation

There is need for a specialist hernia surgeon to work in rural and semi-urban settlements. An advocacy for private-public partnership between governments and the private health sectors will be salutary; this will increase manpower, incentives and provide the rural hospitals with modern medical facilities. This study is limited by short follow up period and technical error inherent in clinical measurements of parameters like hernia defect size. Additionally, the fact that some elective cases were repaired with mesh and others by suture-based techniques may have modified the effects of the predictors. A more robust randomized prospective study with mesh versus non-mesh arms is required to further elucidate the effects of these predictors on the outcomes.

Limitation

This study is limited by the relatively short follow up period and technical error inherent in clinical measurements of parameters like hernia defect size. Additionally, the fact that some elective cases were repaired with mesh and others by suture-based techniques may have modified the effects of the predictors on the postoperative outcomes.

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Conflict of interest: None

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